

Attributing meanings to materials

Elvin Karana and Paul Hekkert

Landbergstraat 15 2628 CE Delft, the Netherlands
e.karana@tudelft.nl; p.p.m.hekkert@tudelft.nl

Abstract

Products convey meanings. A kettle may look sober or a tea cup may strike one as traditional or nostalgic. Various factors can play a role in this meaning construction, such as shape, color, use or user characteristics. In our research, we concentrate on the materials of products. A product may be attributed different meanings through the material it is made of. Simultaneously, a particular material may get different meanings in different products. How a material is evaluated and what kinds of meanings it expresses may have a strong influence on people's appraisals of products. Therefore, understanding materials and how they get their meanings will provide a valuable contribution to the design domain. In this particular study, we aim to find the key variables in meaning attribution to materials. The study consists of three joined studies with three different groups and a thorough assessment of 75 products and their materials. The results of the study are used to build a model covering the key variables that jointly contribute to a material's meaning.

Conference theme: Technology & Materials

Keywords: expressive characteristics, meanings, materials, materials experience

1 Introduction

When we (first) perceive a product, we try to place it into a meaningful category and attention will be drawn to those signs that can help us to identify and categorize it (Krippendorff and Butter, 1984). Materials, being the substance of products, can act as such a sign. They affect the experience in user- product interaction and in a previous study *materials experience* was defined as *the whole series of effects elicited by the interactions between people and materials of products in a particular context* (Karana et al., 2007). Similar to the experience of the product as a whole, materials experience also consists of three experiential components: (1) sensorial (aesthetic) experience, (2) experience of meaning, and (3) emotional experience (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007; Hekkert and Schifferstein, 2008). In this particular study, we focus on one of these experiential

components: the experience of meaning. We explore and discuss the key variables in meaning attribution to materials.

This paper describes a thorough analysis of three different focus group studies on material appraisals of 75 products. In the next section, we first shortly discuss how materials are used for creating meanings and what we mean by ‘meanings of materials’. In the third section, the three focus group studies are described. On the basis of their results, five ways in which materials obtain their meaning are identified in section 4. This classification is finally used to develop a model implying the key variables in meaning attribution to materials.

2 Meanings of Materials

Van Rompay (2005), in his doctoral thesis on *product expression*, states that “*people talk about products in terms of expressive characteristics reflecting personality traits such as modesty and pride*” (p. 19). When people are asked to describe a certain material, they frequently refer to its expressive characteristics and these characteristics are grounded in different aspects of materials (and products). A particular material of a product, for instance, might express professionalism predominantly through its shiny, robust and smooth properties and the product’s sharp edged geometry. Herein, shininess, robustness, smoothness and sharp-edge geometry cooperate and jointly contribute to a material’s expressive character. Expressive characteristics (variously called figurative or abstract characteristics, see Blank et al., 1984) are not factually part of a materials’ physical entity or appearance (i.e. a material is not literally feminine or masculine). An expressive character (or meaning) of a material is based on the interactions between an individual and his/her environment, including the product and its material, and can change over time.

In materials experience, in addition to expressive meanings (e.g. modern, sexy, sober, etc.) certain associative descriptions, which require retrieval from memory and past experiences, can also express particular qualities of materials, such as *toy-like*, *business-like* and *associated with factories*. These descriptions are commonly used in material appraisals and behave like expressive characteristics. Accordingly, meanings of materials in this research consist of expressive/ semantic and specific associative characteristics which are used for defining the qualities of materials. *Meanings of materials* are what we

think about materials, what kind of values we attribute after the initial sensorial input in a particular context.

3 A study on how materials get their meanings

This study aims to reveal what kind of aspects play a crucial role in attributing meanings to materials. The study consists of three focus group studies with different types of participants. The first study was conducted with academics particularly trained in materials in design and product experience, the second study with professional designers and the final one with non- designers. With the second study conducted with professional designers, we aimed to find out certain differences between design practitioners and designers in academia. In both studies, participants emphasized the role of expertise in assessments of particular meanings. After these two studies, a third study was conducted in order to explore the differences between designers and non- designers in their meaning attribution to materials.

The same procedure was followed in all three studies. Each group was asked to focus on the materials of products, and select five of them expressing the given meanings. The meanings selected for this study came from five conceptually different sets of meanings, as identified in previous studies (Karana et al., 2007): *aggressive, nostalgic, professional, sexy* and *toy- like*. The instruction was explained with an example: *“For instance, you found several products expressing the meaning ‘sexy’. You should particularly focus on the material of these products and select one, of which the material plays a dominant role in conveying this meaning.”* Participants were informed that they could bring a visual representation of the product if it was not possible to bring the product itself.

In all three studies, participants were invited to a focus group discussion. They were asked to bring the products (or visual representations of the products) to the discussion. Participants were first asked to group the products based on their meanings. In this way we could get a first impression on the similarities and differences of material properties belonging to the same meaning category. Next, they were asked to explain their choices. Participants contributed to each others’ descriptions and commented on the points they agreed on or not. They were encouraged to discuss the relations between products, materials, and their meaning. After that, products were evaluated separately and participants were asked if the same product would express a different meaning if it were

made of another material. Correspondingly, various aspects that might play a role in the attribution of meanings to materials were discussed intensively. Discussions were audio-recorded and analyzed after the studies.

3.1 Study 1: material appraisals by design researchers

Participants

Seven design researchers participated in Study 1. Four of them were senior PhD students in their last years of research and two were assistant professors, all at the Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering of Delft University of Technology. One participant was working as a consultant on material advice.

Results

Participants explained their selections starting with the most difficult ones. *Aggressive* was stated as the most difficult meaning to convey through materials because they believe that aggressiveness is more related to the use of a product than to its material. Moreover, form and function of a product very much determine the aggressiveness of its material. All participants brought products that have potentially harming effects during use, such as a needle, a stapler, a fork, a model making knife, etc (see Figure 1). *Their choices thus reflected the literal meaning of aggressiveness, in terms of behavior that is intended to cause harm or pain.*

Figure 1: Examples of aggressive products/materials.

Figure 2: An example of a professional product/material.

According to the participants, products conveying ‘toy-like’ and ‘professional’ were rather easy to find. All selected toy-like products were made of light and colorful plastics. In those products, plastics were mostly appraised as surrogate materials replacing metal, wood, etc. in the first, original versions of these products. They mentioned that a particular combination of certain material properties might evoke professionalism. A strong and lightweight coated aluminum in a bottle was evaluated as professional by one of the participants (Figure 2). The same material could be appraised differently if it was heavy. The participant argued “*We know that this bottle is very durable and strong, which conflicts with its lightness. The combination of these two material properties- lightness and strength- conveys the professional meaning in this particular product.*”

Most of the participants agreed on the pleasing effect of the sexy products when they experienced them tactually. On the other hand, the material of a golden flashy g-string, which was brought by another participant, was not considered sexy by the other participants. In this case the intention and the message were conveyed in a very unsubtle way, which was found irritating. Appreciation of a material as sexy was very personal and expressing the individuals’ interests more than other meanings. Moreover, attributing the meaning ‘sexy’ to a material was found very context dependent. The biggest diversity in materials emerged in products selected for the meaning *nostalgic*, which is dominantly based on personal experiences. Nevertheless, a common property among the selected nostalgic materials was that they were all made of natural materials that come from plants or animals, such as wood, leather, stone, bones, etc. and carried a ‘sign’ referring to the past and representing the product’s age, such as scratches on leather, or smell of wood.

3.2 Study 2: material appraisals of professional designers

Participants

Four professional designers from a Dutch design company participated in this study.

Results

All participants agreed that a material of a *professional* product was often clearly supporting the technical function and the use of the product. Moreover, they associated professionalism with coldness and distance, which made them select metal. Moreover, the context in which a material is experienced was mentioned as an important aspect. For instance, a material of a product used in an office environment can be appraised more professional than when it is used in the kitchen. They added that in professional products you rarely find a combination of more than two materials. They gave a few specific materials' names considered professional, such as Kevlar, titanium, smart materials, etc.

A leather armchair, a furry handcuff and a silk women dress, which were selected for the category *sexy*, were all soft in touch. Two of the designers did not find the fluffy handcuff sexy at all. One of them explained that the object was apparently designed for sending a sex message to a specific target group: *"I don't find it sexy because I am opposed to this idea or I am not supporting a kind of sexual experience which involves handcuffs"*. Another designer added that *"rather than sexy, I find it gay-like"*. These comments are similar to the ones for the 'g-string' in the first study (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Similar explanations were made for the g-string and the handcuff.

In the category *sexy* materials, there was a product of which the material was very different from the other selected ones: a light bulb. In contrast to the other selections which directly or indirectly referred to the experience of sex, the bulb was metaphorically representing the designer's personal reflections on sex. In her words, *"the bulb is very delicate... you should handle it very carefully because it can break easily... and its semi-transparency gives it a mysterious feeling in that you can not completely see what is*

happening inside. And although the material is not soft, semi transparency gives the softness effect as well". One of the designers emphasized that the leather chair, the fluffy handcuff and the bulb were combinations of a 'soft' and a 'hard' material. They were all carrying a metal detail in their bodies (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Examples of sexy materials.

Designers associated *aggressiveness* with roughness (Figure 5). They looked for materials or products which may injure the user in an unexpected way. A very rough surface of a wall, for instance, might hurt when a doer rubs the wall with his bare hands.

Figure 5: Examples of aggressive materials.

Even though shape was obviously playing an important role in conveying the meaning *toy-like* (such as in a rubber duck), when designers were asked to imagine the same products made of metal, they said that the product would hardly express the meaning *toy-like* (Figure 6). Moreover, it was very difficult for all participants to avoid the effect of color on their selections. In their words, color was one of the major factors affecting the overall impressions of products and it was almost impossible to look beyond color and evaluate materials and products apart from their colors.

Figure 6: A rubber duck would express a different meaning if it was made of metal.

In general, the designers emphasized that their expertise could have been especially influential in interpreting the meaning *professional*. They stated that because of their design backgrounds they can see the details related to the high- tech manufacturing processes or expensive materials which may have a big influence on communicating professionalism. Additionally, because they follow new events in the design domain, they can recognize a product made of a novel material and appreciate it. On the other hand, the interpretation of sexiness, for instance, may be less affected by the participants' expertise and relies more on personal tastes (or individual differences).

3.3 Study 3: material appraisals of non-designers.

Participants

Four non- designers participated in this study: two secretaries, one electronic engineer and one software programmer.

Results

Metal appeared for the first time in the materials category *sexy*. The product was a sugar bowl made of a round shaped shiny metal (Figure 7). It had a matt plastic nipple-like brim, clearly expressing a sex related image. The participant explained his choice “*The combination of these two materials- very shiny metal and matt plastic- contributes to the sexiness. Especially the plastic brim emphasizes the nipple form. If it was made of one type of material, the effect could be weaker I guess.*” Similar explanations for the effect of combining materials (or creating contrast by using two different materials) were made in Study 2 (see handcuff and bulb).

Figure 7: Example of a sexy product/material.

One of the participants explained that *“products that imitate existing ones look toy-like to me. The imitated aspect can be related to either function or material. Because plastics are used for imitating other materials, I think light plastic versions of originally metal (or wood, glass, ceramics) products convey the meaning toy-like.”* Following this ‘definition’, the participant suggested to change a product’s category (a lamp) from aggressive to toy-like (Figure 8). The lamp, which was brought to fit the category aggressive, was appraised as toy-like after discussions. They emphasized that *“It is meant to be a lamp but not functioning very well. It is meant to be glass but it is plastic. Shortly, it is imitating a glass version which probably works better. Therefore, it is definitely toy-like.”*

Figure 8: A lamp considered toy-like for its glass-like plastic material.

For the designers in study 2, use of a novel material was often a sign of professionalism in products. Moreover, the production details and good surface finishes affected the designers’ decisions. Conversely, non-designers in this study associated professionalism with materials that fulfill their functions well in certain products. They did not mention any production detail, surface finishing or new material in their appraisals of materials.

4 Overall Discussion and Model Building

In general, participants emphasized that it was challenging to evaluate a material of a product rather than the product itself. They recommended a modification in the task as ‘select a material which is aggressive’ instead of ‘select a material of a product which is aggressive’. The important role of the differences among users in attributing meanings to materials was emphasized throughout the whole discussion. Associations with a unique event (like Christmas) or a person (like grandmother) were leading to personal attachments with certain products. Moreover, context was one of the main aspects mentioned in meaning attribution to materials.

Figure 9 shows some example products selected by each group for the given meanings. We could not observe major differences in the selected products between Study 2 and Study 3. We were expecting to find differences between the two groups in their interpretations of professionalism in materials, but only a minor difference was observed. In contrast to the designers, non- designers did not mention any specific new material (or material family).

Even though characteristics of products and materials were obviously ‘collaborating’ for communicating particular meanings, the type of characteristics depended on the intended meaning. For the meaning toy-like, for instance, the lightness of a material and the rounded geometrical shape of the product were working together for conveying the meaning, whereas for the meaning aggressive the hardness and coldness of a material and how it is used were playing an important role. Moreover, one of the most important findings of the study was: *materials obtain their meanings not only based on their technical and sensorial properties, but also on the products they are embodied in, users who use these products and how or in which context they are used.* Below, we summarize this result with five main ways of materials meaning construction.

	GROUP-I researchers	GROUP-II designers	GROUP-III non-designers
aggressive			
nostalgic			
professional			
sexy			
toy-like			

Figure 9: Examples of selected products in the three studies.

*(1) Meanings of materials based on **material properties***

‘Material properties’ cover the characteristics that distinguish a material from other materials. A material can be different from another material through its unique technical properties like strength, elasticity, heat conductivity, etc. that makes us place this material in a particular material family, such as metal. Technical properties of materials are experienced through sensorial properties by users. In other words, sensorial properties of materials appear as moderators in material-user interaction, and they help us to appraise a material and attribute meanings to it. Summarizing, material properties refer to technical and sensorial properties of materials. In this way of meaning construction, two different scenarios can be observed: (1) the material family (e.g. metal, plastics, glass, etc.) has a main effect on a material’s meaning, or (2) a particular sensorial property of a material (e.g. glossiness, roughness, softness, color, etc.) has a main effect on a material’s meaning. In the first case, meanings attributed to a material family often behave like material’s intrinsic qualities, such as metal is cold and distant or wood is warm and homely. In the latter case, a particular sensorial property (or set of properties) results in assigning a certain meaning to a material. For example, smoothness and semi-transparency of a material might together connote sexiness. In this case, both plastics and glass can obtain the meaning sexy (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Smoothness and semi-transparency in two product examples.

The material properties found effective in attributing meanings to materials can be summarized as follow:

Aggressive: hard and strong (materials that allow jaggedness in products), metallic colors, black, cold, rough

Nostalgic: natural materials (paper, leather, wood), old materials (Bakelite, copper)

Professional: new materials (Kevlar, smart materials), cold, smooth, dark colors (black), metallic colors, few materials, combination of certain technical properties for enhancing function (e.g. combining strength and lightness)

Sexy: smooth, silky, velvet-like, fluffy, skin-like, semi-transparent, glossy, combination of materials for emphasizing a part of a product

Toy-like: smooth, light (weight), bright colors (red, blue, green, yellow, orange)

(2) *Meanings of materials affected by **product aspects** (e.g. shape and function)*

In a number of sources, it is emphasized that the selection of a material cannot be separated from the choice of shape (Edwards and Endean, 1990; Roozenburg and Eekels, 1995; Budinski, 1996; Ashby, 2005), which is in itself determined by the function of a product and material. Shape and function of a product in which materials are embodied also affect how we appraise materials. The same kind of plastic, for instance, can be perceived as sober when it is embodied in an office accessory, whereas it can be toy-like in a household product. Likewise, a material can be perceived as aggressive in sharp-edged products, or repetitive shape elements can be associated with ‘teeth’ and ‘biting’, and the materials in these shapes are thus linked to aggressive behavior (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Repetitive shape elements in example products.

In order to obtain a shape, material is subjected to manufacturing processes. According to Ashby (2005), function, material, shape and manufacturing process interact and this interaction lies at the heart of the materials selection process. How a material is processed or what kind of manufacturing techniques are used may have an important effect on the attribution of meanings to materials. This effect is not a direct one, but it is through shape or sensorial properties. For instance, a polishing process (which is a surface treatment process) affects the surface quality of a material, and its consequence may be a change in material’s meaning. In another example, a particular process applied to a material might cause a very thin wall-thickness, which might change the material’s perceived quality.

(3) Meanings of materials affected by user characteristics

The assessment of products and their materials and attributing meanings to them is related to past experiences and personal tastes of users (Krippendorff and Butter, 1984; Mono, 1997; Krippendorff, 2006). In addition, demographic differences such as age, gender, education, income, etc. and cultural backgrounds may affect how people appraise materials and what kind of meanings they attribute to them. Ljungberg and Edwards (2003) explain the changing value of materials for various cultures, such as Scandinavian, Middle European and Mediterranean, with the example of villas made of wood. Although they are quite popular in Scandinavia, in Middle Europe such houses are often met with skepticism. According to Dormer (1990), as another example, some particular cultures do not favor plastics as kitchenware because it contradicts their understanding of what plastics are and how it performs. For example, people of a certain culture may fear that the plastic cooking pot would melt under the food (Dormer, 1990). In this study, we observed that the attribution of the meaning *nostalgic* to a material entails recalling of memories which belong to an individual's life. As a result, any material in any product can be nostalgic for a particular individual (Figure 12). Likewise, a material may evoke the meaning *sexy* for an individual who associates the material with his/her personal sexual experiences.

Figure 12: Any material can be nostalgic for a particular individual.

(4) Meanings of materials affected by use

Consequences of using a material/ product can be very influential in appraisals of materials. Coming back to a previous example, people associate an unexpected harm effect of a product or material with aggressiveness. Material is appraised in a particular use scenario and possible effects are predicted through previous experiences. A rough wall, for instance, is expected to hurt the skin, or a heat-conductive metal handle of a pan is expected to burn one's hand during use (Figure 13). Meanings attributed to a certain material can be derived from these kinds of use cases.

Figure 13: Materials can be appraised based on particular use scenarios.

(5) Meanings of materials affected by context

People give meanings to things on the basis of situations and contexts (Osgood et al., 1957; Mono, 1996; Johnson, 2007). Krippendorff (2006) explains that a dictionary usually lists several meanings of a word. Competent users of the dictionary know which meaning applies to their situation on the basis of the context in which that particular word occurs. He emphasizes that *artefacts mean what their contexts permit* (p. 59). A material, for instance, can be appraised differently in day-light or night light. Considering the effect of light on material's perception, some particular shops provide their customers with changing rooms having lights that can be set to daylight or night light in order to show how fabrics of clothes are perceived in different illumination. Moreover, the variety of applications for materials in product design has remarkably increased over the last decade. A particular material may be embodied in a kitchen appliance as well as in an office accessory. Even though the technical qualities of the material remain the same in both applications, the expressive meanings attributed to the material may differ considerably. Reciprocally, different materials used in a similar context may obtain similar meanings (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: Materials used in an office environment can be appraised as professional.

Meanings of Materials Model

The Meanings of Materials (MoM) model in **Figure 15** depicts the five ways in which materials can obtain their meanings. A **user** with his/her particular characteristics appraises a material of a product and attributes a meaning (or meanings) to it. The appraised material can be directly based on the material's technical and sensorial properties (presented as (*m*): **material properties** in the model), and affected by the aspects of the *product* in which the material is embodied (presented as (*s*): **shape** and (*f*): **function**), and how it is used (presented as (*u*): **use**).

Figure 15: Meanings of Materials Model.

The model further shows that each aspect is influenced by other aspects, with an exception of **manufacturing process** (mp) that only interacts with shape (Ashby, 2005), but has no direct effect on the meanings of materials. Finally, *the context* in which the material of the product is appraised may have a considerable effect on meanings attributed to materials, and it encloses the entire process of meaning attribution in the model.

5 Conclusion

The main goal of this study was to explore *how people attribute meanings to materials*. Certain sensorial properties of materials can be effective in how materials obtain their meanings. While hard and smooth materials, for instance, are mostly associated with

professionalism, soft and semi transparent materials are found sexy. However, the appraisal of a material embodied in a product is affected by some other aspects, such as the product's shape and function, how it is used in a particular context, and user characteristics. Moreover, the degree to which each aspect contributes to the creation of a particular meaning of a material depends on the type of meaning. Therefore, it is not easy (if not impossible) to define a one- to- one relationship between certain materials and particular meanings. However, our attempt is to draw attention to key aspects that are expected to be effective in meaning attribution to materials. The Meanings of Materials model represents the key aspects as found in this study. In further studies we aim to verify the Meanings of Materials Model with more quantitative studies.

References

- Ashby, M. F. (2005). "Materials Selection in Mechanical Design". 3rd Ed. Oxford: Butterworth- Heinemann.
- Blank, P., Massey, C., Gardner, H., and Winner, E. (1984). "Perceiving what painting express". In W. R. Crozier and A. J. Chapman (Eds.), *Cognitive process in the perception of art* (pp. 127- 143). Amsterdam, Holland.
- Budinski, K. G. (1996). "Engineering Materials: Properties and Selection". 5th Ed. New Jersey, USA: Prentice-Hall.
- Desmet, P.M.A. & Hekkert, P. (2007). "Framework of product experience". *International Journal of Design*, 1, 57-66.
- Dormer, P. (1990). "The Meanings of Modern Design: Towards the Twenty-First Century". Thames and Hudson: London, 62- 70.
- Edwards, L. and Endean, M. (1990). "Manufacturing with Materials". Butterworths: London.
- Hekkert, P. & Schifferstein, H.N.J. (2008). Introducing product experience. In: H.N.J. Schifferstein and P. Hekkert (Eds.), *Product experience*, pp. 1-8. Amsterdam: Elsevier.
- Johnson, M. (2007). "The Meaning of the Body: Aesthetic of Human Understanding". The University of Chicago Press, USA.
- Karana, E., Hekkert, P.P.M. and Kandachar, P.V. (2007). "Sensorial Properties of Materials for Creating Expressive Meanings". *Kansei Engineering and Emotion Research Conference 2007*, Sapporo, Japan.
- Krippendorff, K. (2006). "The Semantic Turn: A New Foundation for Design". Taylor & Francis Group, USA.

Krippendorff, K. and Butter, R. (1984). "Product Semantics: Exploring the Symbolic Qualities of Form", *The Journal of the Industrial Designers Society of America*; spring: 4-9.

Ljungberg, L. Y. and Edwards, K. L. (2003). "Design, materials selection and marketing of successful products". *Materials and Design* 2003; 24: 519-529.

Mono, R. (1997). "Design for Product Understanding: the aesthetics of design from a semiotic approach". Skogs Boktryckeri AB: Sweden.

Osgood, C.E., Suci, G.J. and Tannenbaum, P.H. (1957). "The Measurement of Meaning". University of Illinois Press: USA.

Roozenburg, N.F.M and Eekels, J. (1995). "Product Design: Fundamentals and Methods". Wiley, Chichester: UK.

Van Rompay T. (2005). "Expressions: Embodiment in the Experience of Design". Delft University of Technology: the Netherlands.